

MEMORANDUM

DATE: 30 SEPTEMBER 2021

TO: THE CLERK TO THE COMMITTEE
COMMITTEE ON CONSTITUTIONAL, LEGAL AND PARLIAMENTARY AFFAIRS
OFFICE OF PARLIAMENT
OSU - ACCRA

THROUGH: Daowusu-agyekum@parliament.gh

FROM: A [REDACTED] P [REDACTED]

SUBJECT: BILL FOR THE PROMOTION OF PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS AND
GHANAIAN FAMILY VALUES, 2021

This is a memorandum in support of the Bill for the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values.

Though the LGBTQ community has gained a voice to demand public and global acceptance for their sexual preferences and practices; with funding and support from wealthy western nations and corporations, I personally object to this for the following reasons:

1. The practice is Godless in that it rejects the Creator, who created mankind with only two biological genders: Male and Female. It spurns long held Ghanaian cultural and religious foundations and beliefs on the sanctity of life, Life as a gift, and sex assigned at birth, in place of personal sexual preference.
2. The LGBTQ practice is Lawless by the fact that it places personal preference above biological morphology, form and function and social practice. Thus it spurns the Creator who made male and female and commanded both to be fruitful, multiply and replenish the earth. The male copulatory organ is morphologically suited for the female's and vice versa.
3. This practice is Irresponsible. It elevates the so called rights of the LGBTQ community without considering the associated impact and responsibility on the individual and the individual toward society, i.e. infections resulting from the combination of body fluids which would be naturally segregated, anal incontinence, long term effect on the family, society and preservation of the human race in natural procreation.
4. The practice is Unnatural. Preservation of the human race has been by natural, normal and proper heterosexual procreation over the centuries. By the natural process other creatures of creation have been preserved for humanity. Scientific advances, restricted to a few members of society may privilege individuals to engage in hormonal therapies and surgery to change their natural sexual organs, however it cannot validate LGBTQ practice as normal and natural.
5. The practice is Psychologically Irrational. As human beings, we classify and name things as part of our existence. The natural sex of a mammal is identified at birth. With the LGBTQ practice we are made to understand that an individual can change sexual orientation mentally and or naturally during the lifetime of the individual.

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These points are in no way exhaustive, I hope to have brought my support to the introduction of the Bill for the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values, 2021.